

THE CLASSIFICATION OF NATIONAL VALUES IN THE PROSE OF SHUKUR KHOLMIRZAEV

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the artistic features of the reflection of national values in the prose of Shukur Kholmirzaev and their classification. Attention is paid to how the writer's works reflect traditions, moral norms, spiritual heritage and ways of understanding the national identity of the Uzbek people. The article, based on ideological and artistic analysis, examines the values expressed in the writer's prose works - such concepts as responsibility, kindness, honor, patriotism. Also, the historical, social and spiritual roots of national values are consistently highlighted, the author's aesthetic views are revealed in their depiction.*

Keywords: *national values, Uzbek prose, artistic analysis, spiritual heritage, moral norms, patriotism, self-awareness, artistic image, writer's skill, human nature.*

Introduction

National values are an integral part of the cultural and spiritual heritage of each nation, leaving a deep mark on the social life of society and the consciousness of individuals. Literature is an important tool for expressing, preserving and developing national values. From this point of view, the study of the reflection and classification of national values in modern Uzbek prose is of great importance.

The work of the people's writer of Uzbekistan Shukur Kholmirzaev occupies a unique place in Uzbek literature in the artistic coverage of national identity, traditional morality and spiritual values. In his works, the historical experience, moral principles and social values of our people are widely represented through various images and events. Therefore, a deep analysis of the classification of national values and their artistic embodiment in the prose of Shukur Kholmirzaev is necessary.

This article is devoted to this problem and analyzes how national values are classified in the work of Shukur Kholmirzaev and what artistic means they are revealed in his works. The results of the analysis allow us to more fully understand national values and their place in modern Uzbek prose.

Methodology

In the analysis of the prose works of Shukur Kholmirzaev, literary-analytical and comparative methods were used to study the classification and artistic embodiment of national values. In the process of analysis, the main attention was paid to the analysis of the text of the works and the images, symbols, motifs and stylistic means presented in it. For a deep understanding of the text and its analysis in the socio-spiritual context, a hermeneutic approach was used.

Also, methods of historical and conceptual analysis were widely used to determine the connection of Shukur Kholmirzaev's work with the Uzbek national culture and traditional values. In this direction, a classification of national values in the author's works was carried out, their place and significance in modern Uzbek prose were highlighted.

Results and analysis

In the process of analyzing the writer's works, various layers of national values in the prose works of Shukur Kholmirzaev were identified and classified. The most important of them were: family and family traditions, national language and culture, national history and historical memory, spirituality and religious values, as well as moral principles such as humanity and kindness.

In the author's work, national values are deeply expressed not only through artistic symbols, but also through the characters, their life choices and inner experiences. This gives the work philosophical depth and spiritual richness.

The artistic classification of national values in the works of Shukur Kholmirzaev opens up new directions in the modern context of Uzbek prose. The author shows the need to preserve national values, their renewal and development against the background of global processes. At the same time, the harmony of nationality and humanity occupies a central place in the works.

It was revealed that the work of Shukur Kholmirzaev is of great importance for strengthening national values in literature, passing them on to the younger generation and preserving the wealth of Uzbek culture. This gives his prose a special place and role in modern Uzbek literature.

Uzbek literary criticism at one time drew attention to the innovative aspects of Sh. Kholmirzaev's work. The famous literary scholar M. Koshzhonov wrote: "Shukur sometimes peers into relationships invisible to the eye among his contemporaries, and looks for meaning that can become a lesson for readers in relationships that, at first glance, are not important to him" [8, 358]. This was a high assessment given at the right time. Therefore, attention to the assessment of the writer's work as a poetic phenomenon began in the 60s.

Each work of Shukur Kholmirzaev in its own way illuminates national, universal human values. For example, the mental state of the old man Kozivoy ("Old Man") is a phenomenon that can occur in almost all of humanity. Approaching old age or as a result of a serious illness, a person begins to worry about approaching death. In the case of an old man separated from his wife and having no children, this law of life found its convincing illustration. The idea put forward in the story is of a universal nature. That is, as long as man exists, death is inevitable. But how does man meet death according to national principles? In this matter, man's attitude to ancient traditions is of primary importance. From this point of view, in the story "The Old Man" the writer managed to convey a universal human idea, clothed in a national form, based on the hero's Islamic beliefs. The story expresses an important universal human truth that has social value: the struggle for survival, honest work and passion for life.

Sh. Kholmirzaev is a writer with a unique style in modern Uzbek prose. The breadth of the spiritual world of the heroes of his works, the embodiment of the hero as a child of the local environment and the generalization of an entire nation in himself, as well as the elevation of national feelings in the character of the hero to the level of universal human values are qualities directly related to the style of the writer.

Most of the stories of Shukur Kholmirzaev are devoted to the artistic analysis of spiritual problems. The story "If a heavy stone moves ..." [11, 106] is one of such stories.

The basis of the story is a discussion that began with the fact that the chairman of the collective farm Shoberdi Murodov, ignoring his school friend, teacher Yesonboy, treated him with contempt and shook his hand; the analysis of the conversation with the participation of friends-

journalists and artists is not just a writer's confusion around a small topic. Here the writer raises two important questions. In this story, written in 1970, the writer, firstly, sharply denounced the society that ignores the sacred profession of a teacher, and the leader who disrespects the owner of this profession. Secondly, no matter how the owner of this profession fights for his dignity, one of the heroes of the work, the Artist, says that people who do not obey in life and know how to defend their dignity are valued, he artistically expressed the fact that the future of society is brought up by teachers in such a situation, and that this situation must be changed.

In the collection "If a heavy stone moves from its place..." there is a story "The Law of Attraction of the Universe" [11, 367]. This story also touches on a spiritual and moral problem. The story depicts the image of Khusan-aki, who deceived himself almost all his life, believing that the meaning of life is to make friends and acquaintances, and to brag to others. His character is such that even in pursuit of his liver to the final destination, he does not give up this habit. Shukur Kholmiraev is a master of creating such a tragedy of laughter or funny tragedy in most of his stories. In such works, he does not at all strive to make the reader laugh, but does not put him in a tragic position either. His main goal is to describe the hero as he is, without interference, impartially. The writer gives the reader the opportunity to draw conclusions from this story himself. Reading such stories, the reader does not notice how involuntarily begins to analyze them, to think about the heroes.

"The Law of Universal Gravitation" and its hero are exactly like that. Life is fair and merciless. The time of Khusan-aki will come. Only in the last moments, on the eve of farewell to life, his true essence is revealed. Closing his eyes, he does not stop looking at the friends and acquaintances around him. The last rays of light pierce his heart.

Sh. Kholmiraev's characters strengthened the spirit of the heroes in the Uzbek story, especially their dissatisfaction with themselves and the desire for a deeper understanding of themselves. In this sense, the writer sets his main goal not to describe the actions of his heroes in public life, but their intellect. In the writer's understanding, intellect is the core of the hero. Therefore, the writer is more interested in the actions of the hero and the process of revealing his intellect in relation to a given event and its outcome than in the actions of the hero and the outcome of the event underlying the work. In such cases, some of Sh. Kholmiraev's stories and the characters of their heroes leave the impression that they evoke an uncertain and contradictory attitude not only in the heart of the reader or critic, but sometimes in the author of the work himself. In particular, this can be said about the story "Once Upon a Time". The endless torment in the heart of the driver Osar - the search for the soul, the instability of the inner world, the conflict of views on the past and the present, on himself and his wife, which led to the departure of his grandmother to distant lands, and the mental suffering he experienced - all these are the hero's attempts to understand himself.

In the story "Once Upon a Time", Shukur Kholmiraev was one of the first in our literature to artistically embody the influence of these recent changes and difficulties occurring in society on the human heart.

The situation has reached the point that even the character of rural residents, whose age-old traditions and customs are quite strong and which are difficult to change, began to change. This is due to the influence of deprivation, helplessness and nervousness in the family, environment and circumstances. As described in the story "Once Upon a Time" [10, 25], some of these changes were not noticeable in the character of the people until recently.

Grandma raised her grandson on her own. She fed him, watered him, married him off and made a home for him. Hard times – the difficulty of making ends meet, poverty, the sharp tongue of her daughter-in-law and the lack of domestic conversation – threw the family into daily turmoil. On top of all this, Grandma was growing old, losing her mind and becoming increasingly restless. As if that were not enough, she was struck by a foul-smelling disease. The family and the house were in a state of nervousness, the situation was difficult, the sky was distant and the earth was harsh.

No matter how patient Osar was, no matter how hard he endured, circumstances and circumstances inclined him to change. Grandma, who had whites of her eyes, seemed to do too much for herself, her food and her wife. As a result, the devil gets lost and breaks a strong national tradition that has existed for centuries. One day, Osar leaves his grandmother in a deserted place from where he cannot return. This is the reason why the young man's nerves cannot withstand the hardships of life.

However, the writer does not finish his work here. After all, his goal is not only to show the hardships of time and spiritual changes in the hero, but also to show that love for people does not fade in the human heart and in the veins of the nation.

No matter how patient Osar is, no matter how steadfastly he endures difficulties, circumstances and circumstances change his nature. It seemed to him that his grandmother, who was the apple of his eye, does too much for himself, his food and his wife. As a result, the devil gets lost and violates a strong national tradition that has developed over the centuries. One day, Osar leaves his grandmother in a deserted place from where he cannot return. This is the reason why the young man's nerves become unbearable due to the hardships of marriage.

"- Grandma! — the grandson said in a hoarse voice, and he cried out after a long cry: — Your younger brother is calling you! Younger brother!.. One of them said...

— Who? — the old woman whispered, and her face lit up, and her eyes sparkled. — Younger brother?

— Yes! You are invited to visit! — said Osar, heading for the door in a plain robe and with a chain on top" [12, 87].

However, the writer does not end his work here. After all, his goal is not only to show the severity of the time and the spiritual turning point of the hero, but also to show that love for a person never fades in the human heart, in the veins of a nation.

The reader cannot hide his hatred for both Osar and his wife for what they did. At the same time, he begins to analyze the circumstances that led them to this situation, without realizing it, and comes to the correct conclusion that such an attitude towards the old woman is still impossible.

Osar and his wife realize their bitter mistake: they go in search of the old woman.

“— The old woman ... — he said in a breaking voice. — After all ... — And then he remembered how the old woman laughed (when Osar left) and said: “That's how it was ...”, and thought: “If someone else took me for granted ...”. And he remembered that he - Osarnia - would not recognize himself, and helplessly whispered:

— She went crazy "[12, 91].

At this point, the writer brings the story to a climax. The old woman is no longer there. She was taken away by unknown, kind people. Is it possible to bear these pangs of conscience now? In this way, the writer strengthens his heroes in eternal torment for their actions.

The writer puts a lot of meaning into the ending of the work. Other people take Grandma to their shelter. It should be understood that the main content of the idea of the work, in a certain sense, lies precisely in these people. As long as there are people who are almost invisible in the story, who do not participate in it, life does not fade away, love does not die, the nation is not humiliated.

Revealing the universal essence of an artistic image requires great skill from the writer. Literary critic Khurshid Dostmukhamedov, discussing Sh. Kholmiraev's story "Once Upon a Time", expressed an important thought on this matter: "... And what if those who fanatically demand the preservation of the national spirit in a work of art look at the problem from this point of view? No sane person denies nationality, but for artistic thinking, elevated to the universe, is not the process of turning to universal, eternal truths more blessed than to narrow national values?" [1, 139]. In our opinion, depicting universal truths is a blessed process for a writer. However, we should not forget that universal truths become even deeper when they are revealed through a national context, through the thoughts, experiences and actions of national heroes.

The hero of Adib's novel "The Last Stop". The hero of Adib's novel "The Last Stop", Sabahat, who grew up on folk songs, treats national traditions with a different love and considers himself responsible for their preservation. He sees the customs of the people beating the cedar and singing dhikr in Chigatai, Kenagas and Ola Chopone, and becomes interested in cedar singing and dhikr. He strives to write down the text. Having discerned a talent for poetry and versification in his student Boybori, he regularly repeats the following words to him: "The people of the poet must be close to the people, you need to know their spirit. The spirit of the people is reflected first of all in their tales and oral works" [13, 156]. "If you want to become a poet, collect and study folk terms! Let their melodies and rhymes be imprinted in your heart!" [13, 157].

In his novel, the writer strives to show the problems of the era in which he lives, especially the fact that the people are losing their identity, breaking away from their past and losing everything through symbols.

The fact that one of the heroes of the novel, Kuvvatbekov, although he dreams of leaving for Tashkent, remains in Bekat and carries out educational work, and Munira, also remaining in Bekat, gets a job as a history teacher at the Mahmud Kashgari school and reveals the secret of Ajinatepa, is a symbolic indication of the implementation of the great goal of the work - the education of youth through historical consciousness and historical memory. Even in the performance of an ancient, now forgotten custom of the highlanders at the funeral of Sabahat, recorded by his student Boybori, we see the implementation of the goal of returning to identity.

Events such as Oktam's break with Nasiba, his demolition of the old garden and the construction of a new one after much hesitation, as well as Shamshiddinov's realization after a short conversation with Munira that the human soul needs balm and the decision to treat it with medicinal herbs for free, should be assessed not only as "the awakening of conscience and the superiority of humanity over spirituality," but also as the people's appeal to enlightenment, the revival of historical memory and the desire for freedom and emancipation.

Closer to the truth, Iskhok's courage towards the old man Barot is also seen as a rebellion of faith against atheism, the superiority of compassionate feelings over satanic impulses. Nasiba's transformation into another person, expressed through Oktam's alienated gaze, and Sadyk's flight from Bekat also contain symbolic meanings. In general, Bekat is a part of the "endless lands" inhabited by Uzbeks, and the people living there are a microcosm of the so-called

Uzbek nation of the "Soviet people". The changes that occur in Bekat at the end of the work - the retreat of evil and the triumph of good, the departure of evil and the survival of good, spiritual awakening and activity of people - all this was the dream of the great writer.

Conclusion

In general, the results of the analysis of the classification of national values and their artistic embodiment in the prose works of Shukur Kholmirzaev showed that the author deeply reveals the main aspects of the Uzbek national culture and history through his prose works, sheds new light on national values in the modern context.

In the work of Shukur Kholmirzaev, national values are manifested not only as historical or cultural information, but also as a complex and multifaceted concept, closely related to humanism, spirituality and moral standards. Therefore, his prose works harmoniously reflect the principles of nationalism and humanism. As a result, the works of Shukur Kholmirzaev are an important source in the study and systematization of national values, making their artistic and spiritual contribution to the development of modern Uzbek prose. This makes his works an important literary heritage in the preservation and development of national culture.

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